

National Open Access Monitor Project

Defining Requirements Survey: Scope Report

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16 March 2023

This document relates to the 'Scope of the National Open Access Monitor' section of the 'National Open Access Monitor Survey: Defining Requirements' which was carried out between February 2-28th 2023 under the National Open Access Monitor Project, funded by Ireland's National Open Research Forum (NORF) under the NORF Open Research Fund 2022 to address one of the six priority actions of Ireland's [National Action Plan for Open Research 2022-2023](#).

More information on the survey is available here: <https://irel.ie/oamonitor-february2023survey/>. A PDF of the survey is available here: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7588787>

This document details the logic behind the opening proposal that the tender for the development of the National Open Access Monitor specifies that the Monitor:

1. uses the Budapest Open Access Initiative definition of "open access"
2. uses the UnPaywall definition of "open access types"
3. initially focuses on monitoring peer-reviewed articles and conference proceedings
4. has the potential in the future to expand to monitor monographs, book chapters, other scholarly publication outputs, open research activities and measures (to be defined during [Action 6.2.3](#), expected in 2025-2027)
5. focuses on publications which can be uniquely and unambiguously identified by a DOI
6. defines an "Irish scholarly publication" as a publication which contains the unique persistent identifier of an Irish organisation in the publication and/or the publication metadata and/or the persistent identifier metadata.

The following logic was detailed within the survey and respondents were invited to agree or disagree and propose an alternative.

1. DEFINITION OF OPEN ACCESS

Context: the NORF 2022 Open Research Fund [Call for Expressions of Interest](#) specifically tasked this National Open Access Monitoring project to "Work to arrive at a community-agreed definition for Open Access at the national level".

It is acknowledged that the [NORF National Open Research Landscape Report](#) references the [Berlin Declaration on Open Access to Knowledge in the Sciences and Humanities](#) in National Framework Recommendations 8 and 14.

"NFR 8: OA publications must be accompanied by an open licence, preferably the Creative Commons Attribution licence, CC BY, or another appropriate Creative Commons licence, such as CC BY-SA or CC0. Licensing terms should not unduly restrict text and data mining, in accordance with and without prejudice to applicable copyright legislation. The licence applied should fulfil the requirements defined by the Berlin Declaration on Open Access."

"NFR 14: The importance of open archives and repositories for hosting research outputs is acknowledged due to their sustained role in enabling open access over many years, their archiving and long-term preservation function, and their potential for editorial innovation. In line with the Berlin Declaration on Open Access, and via the National Action Plan, Irish stakeholders will ensure that a complete final version of each publication is made accessible and preserved via an online repository maintained by an academic institution, scholarly society, government agency, or other well-established organisation that seeks to enable open access, unrestricted distribution, interoperability, fault tolerance, immutability, and long-term archiving."

The [Berlin Declaration](#) definition states:

"Open access contributions must satisfy two conditions:

1. The author(s) and right holder(s) of such contributions grant(s) to all users a free, irrevocable, worldwide, right of access to, and a license to copy, use, distribute, transmit and display the work publicly and to make and distribute derivative works, in any digital medium for any responsible purpose, subject to proper attribution of authorship (community standards, will continue to provide the mechanism for enforcement of proper attribution and responsible use of the published work, as they do now), as well as the right to make small numbers of printed copies for their personal use.
2. A complete version of the work and all supplemental materials, including a copy of the permission as stated above, in an appropriate standard electronic format is deposited (and thus published) in at least one online repository using suitable technical standards (such as the Open Archive definitions) that is supported and maintained by an academic institution, scholarly society, government agency, or other well established organization that seeks to enable open access, unrestricted distribution, interoperability, and long term archiving."

However, the [NORF National Action Plan](#) does not directly align with the Berlin Declaration, as it states:

"We support multi track policies and pathways to open access, enabling both repository-mediated (also known as Green OA) and publisher-mediated (Gold OA) routes, without an embargo period. [...] Authors should retain sufficient rights to enable full and immediate open access via the Green or Gold route."

Therefore, it is not possible to adopt the Berlin Declaration, which requires repository deposit as a requirement to be "open access", when NORF has stated that publisher mediated open access is also supported under the National Action Plan to 100% open access.

It is therefore proposed that the [Budapest Open Access Initiative](#) (BOAI) definition is adopted. It states:

"By "open access" to this literature, we mean its free availability on the public internet, permitting any users to read, download, copy, distribute, print, search, or link to the full texts of these articles, crawl them for indexing, pass them as data to software, or use them for any other lawful purpose, without financial, legal, or technical barriers other than those inseparable from gaining access to the internet itself."

3. DEFINITION OF OPEN ACCESS TYPES

[The NORF Open Access Monitoring Policy Brief](#) states "Unpaywall is widely used and its definitions are seen as a de facto standard." For a detailed listing of all integrations using UnPaywall, see [here](#).

For the purpose of the National Open Access Monitor, it is proposed to use the [UnPaywall standard](#) to define "open access type", to enable the Monitor distinguish between the different types of open access.

Specifically:

"Green articles are published in toll-access journals, but archived in an OA archive, or "repository". These repositories may be discipline-specific (like ArXiv) or institutional repositories operated by universities or other institutions. Green articles may be published versions or preprints, and can have any license or no license.

Bronze articles are free to read on the publisher's website, without a license that grants any other rights. There may be a delay between publication and availability to read, and often articles can be removed unilaterally by the publisher.

Hybrid articles are free to read at the time of publication, with an open license. These are usually published in exchange for an article processing charge, or APC.

Gold articles have all the same characteristics as Hybrid articles, but are published in all-Open Access journals, which are in turn called "Gold journals", or just "OA journals".

The [National Open Research Landscape Report](#), National Framework Recommendation 8 states:

"OA publications must be accompanied by an open licence, preferably the Creative Commons Attribution licence, CC BY, or another appropriate Creative Commons licence, such as CC BY-SA or CC0. Licensing terms should not unduly restrict text and data mining, in accordance with and without prejudice to applicable copyright legislation. The licence applied should fulfil the requirements defined by the Berlin Declaration on Open Access."

The [UnPaywall definition](#) of open licenses aligns with this NORF definition:

- Any [Creative Commons](#) license.
- Public Domain / [CC0](#)
- [ACS Editors' Choice](#)
- [APS License for Accepted Manuscripts](#)
- [Open Access for APA Journals Authors](#)
- Many other less-common licenses, as long as they grant users sufficient rights to freely use and redistribute content.

3. SCOPE: PUBLICATION TYPES

1. The [National Action Plan](#) states:

"Our aim is to implement a sustainable and inclusive course for achieving 100% open access to research publications by 2030 [...] For academic books, it is recognised that some stakeholders may permit embargo periods, but these should be as short as possible. [...]."

2. The [National Open Landscape Report](#) states:

"NFR 1: All Irish scholarly publications resulting from publicly funded research will be openly available by default from 2020 onwards and will be accessible on an ongoing basis. It is recognised that the timeline to achieve open access for publications other than journal articles and conference proceedings, e.g. monographs and book chapters, may take longer."

3. The [National Action Plan](#) states "In the implementation of this plan, particularly in terms of infrastructure, actions should be guided by the principles outlined in the UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science. The [UNESCO Recommendation](#) defines "scientific publications" as follows:

"Scientific publications that include, among others, peer-reviewed journal articles and books, research reports and conference papers. Scientific publications may be disseminated by publishers on open access online publishing platforms and/or deposited and made immediately accessible in open online repositories upon publication, that are supported and

maintained by an academic institution, scholarly society, government agency or other well established not-for-profit organization devoted to common good that enables open access, unrestricted distribution, interoperability and long-term digital preservation and archiving. Scientific outputs related to publications (e.g. original scientific research results, research data, software, source code, source materials, workflows and protocols, digital representations of pictorial and graphical materials and scholarly multimedia material) that are openly licensed or dedicated to the public domain should be deposited in a suitable open repository, following appropriate technical standards that allow them to be properly linked to publications. A paywalled method of publication, where immediate access to scientific publications is only granted in exchange for payment, is not aligned with the present Recommendation. Any transfer or licensing of copyrights to third parties should not restrict the public's right to immediate open access to a scientific publication."

4. The NORF 2022 Open Research Fund [Call for Expressions of Interest](#) specifically referenced [Science Europe's briefing paper on Open Access Monitoring](#) as background information for this National Open Access Monitor project. This states:

"Peer-reviewed scholarly articles published in journals are, by far, the most analysed type of academic publication. Standardised workflows of article publishing and discovery have resulted in well developed infrastructures, providing general and Open Access specific metadata. Hence, scholarly articles are the least challenging type of publication to monitor and have been the focus of every large-scale monitoring exercise to date. Going beyond the scholarly article might require additional approaches to gather, analyse, and interpret publication data. Open Access to academic books is at an earlier stage of development and the publishing landscape differs considerably from that of scholarly articles. To monitor the publication status of books, book chapters, and proceedings, additional metadata are needed. For example, to differentiate between editors of books or anthologies and authors of individual contributions. The infrastructures and data sources for other types are not yet as developed as they are for articles."

Proposal

Therefore, it is proposed that peer-reviewed journal articles and conference proceedings are initially prioritised to be monitored by the National Open Access Monitor; but that the Monitor must have the potential in the future to expand to monitor monographs, book chapters, other scholarly publication outputs, open research activities and measures (to be defined during [Action 6.2.3](#), expected in 2025-2027)

4. SCOPE: PERSISTENT IDENTIFIERS (IDENTIFYING PUBLICATIONS)

1. The [National Action Plan](#) action 4.4 is defined as "Invest in Persistent Identifier infrastructure to enable consistent monitoring and improve interoperability". A4.4.2 is defined as "Develop a national roadmap for the adoption of a range of Persistent Identifiers according to international best practice, such as ORCID, DOIs, RAIDs and ROR identifiers."

2. The [NORF National Landscape Report](#) defines National Framework Recommendation 12 as:

"Open access publications should be easily identifiable by appropriate technical means, defined through the National Action Plan. This will include the availability of specific metadata, interoperability standards, and persistent identifiers. Such metadata should be available for reuse under a suitable open licence. Data on citations (references from one publication to another) should be made available as openly licensed, structured metadata.""

3. The [National Open Access Monitoring Policy Brief](#) states:

"Identifiers have a crucial role to play in monitoring, with Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) being the basis for much of the existing monitoring through Unpaywall. It is important that all output has some form of unique identifier. [...] PIDs, or Persistent Identifiers are unique, machine-readable identifications which are associated with a specific entity, output or actor in the research process (e.g. author, institution, publication, grant, etc.). This allows for disambiguation which ensures that there is no confusion between the scholarly output of two authors with the same name, for example. This is critical in terms of analysing any substantial publication dataset. Systematic adoption of PIDs (such as ORCID IDs, RAIDs, Crossref and DataCite DOIs, and ROR identifiers) across the Irish research sector will enable automation and foster efficiencies and cost saving etc. in OA monitoring [...]."

4. [Science Europe's briefing paper on Open Access Monitoring](#) states: "Current monitoring workflows already rely on widely available Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) for publications."

"Organisations conducting a monitoring exercise should consider the following when gathering and interpreting data on publications [...] For publications, DOIs are required"

Therefore, it is proposed that the National Open Access Monitor focuses on publications which can be uniquely and unambiguously identified by a DOI.

5. SCOPE: PERSISTENT IDENTIFIERS (DEFINING IRISH SCHOLARLY PUBLICATIONS)

Context:

- The NORF 2022 Open Research Fund [Call for Expressions of Interest](#) specifically -tasked this National Open Access Monitor project to "Work with external partners to deliver reports and a national dashboard **to help Ireland publish, analyse and track OA rates at the national level.**" [emphasis added]
- The National Action Plan, chapter 4 is "Achieving 100% open access to **research publications**", which states: "In line with Ireland's National Framework on the Transition to an Open Research Environment, we reaffirm the national objective that all **Irish scholarly publications** resulting from publicly funded research will be openly available by default." [emphasis added].

Therefore, to identify "Irish scholarly publications" for the purpose of national monitoring, it is proposed to utilise persistent identifiers:

1. The [National Action Plan](#) action 4.4 is defined as "Invest in Persistent Identifier infrastructure to enable consistent monitoring and improve interoperability".

A4.4.1 is defined as "Support the Irish ORCID Consortium and encourage further development and adoption of ORCID according to international best practice by researchers and within the systems and processes of publishers, research performing organisations, research funding organisations, and infrastructures."

A4.4.2 is defined as "Develop a national roadmap for the adoption of a range of Persistent Identifiers according to international best practice, such as ORCID, DOIs, RAIDs and ROR identifiers."

2. The [National Open Access Monitoring Policy Brief](#) states:

"Identifiers have a crucial role to play in monitoring, with Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) being the basis for much of the existing monitoring through Unpaywall. It is important that all output has some form of unique identifier. [...] PIDs, or Persistent Identifiers are unique, machine-readable identifications which are associated with a specific entity, output or actor in the research process (e.g. author, institution, publication, grant, etc.).

This allows for disambiguation which ensures that there is no confusion between the scholarly output of two authors with the same name, for example. This is critical in terms of analysing any substantial publication dataset.

Systematic adoption of PIDs (such as ORCID IDs, RAIDs, Crossref and DataCite DOIs, and ROR identifiers) across the Irish research sector will enable automation and foster efficiencies and cost saving etc. in OA monitoring [...]."

3. "In deciding on what should be monitored, definitions will need to be agreed not just on what counts as Open Access, but on what constitutes an Irish publication. The IReL deals providing open access to many Irish institutional authors rely on a corresponding author's affiliation; this may prove an additional complication over existing monitoring solutions where any author's affiliated Irish institution is used to signify an Irish publication."

4. [Science Europe's briefing paper on Open Access Monitoring](#) states:

"The minimum requirement to attribute a publication to a RPO should be a specific affiliation of any of its authors, irrespective of the author's position in the author line. To attribute a publication to a RFO there should be an acknowledgement of the received funding in the publication itself."

"Organisations conducting a monitoring exercise should consider the following when gathering and interpreting data on publications [...] For institutions, services such as the community-led Research Organization Registry (ROR) should be used. For funding sources, services such as Crossref's Funder Registry are recommended."

Therefore, it is proposed that the National Open Access Monitor defines an "Irish scholarly publication" as a publication which contains the unique persistent identifier of an Irish organisation in the publication and/or the publication metadata and/or the persistent identifier metadata.